

ROLE OF INNOVATION IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Ibodullaev Dostonbek Sobirjon ugli

Deputy Chief Accountant at the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

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Currently, innovation is the most characteristic of economic development is becoming one of its features. Recently, this name is exotic, unknown and even reminded me of something not so clear even among professionals, but now the innovation itself and its concepts are rapidly conquering the world. The international capital market that transforms into a resource is expanding, in this respect it is new financial structures are helping him.

The experience of developed countries shows that innovation often direct negative attitude and position of people is hindered. However, in Uzbekistan a paradoxical situation is developing, that is, the whole society is positive towards innovative processes expressing attitude and support.

Innovative development of the economy, by creating new entrepreneurs the purpose of the research work is to help increase the potential and efficiency of the system is considered The tasks of the research are competitiveness and productivity in the industry researching the stages of growth and justifying its specific features; high stimulating the increase in the share of technological products, increasing production and increasing share in production and export, innovative technologies and advanced is to determine the factors affecting the expansion of the use of management.

Analysis of literature on the topic:

According to some authors, the traditional economy is based on a different basis there is also a developing new economy. In our opinion, it would be appropriate to use the positive aspects of both of these models without contrasting them, because it shows that a new one is gradually developing at the heart of the traditional economy. Indeed, in the modern world, innovation has become a factor of production is true. It is known that traditionally there are three factors of production: land, labor and capital. J.B. Sey was the first to analyze them. Currently, these factors usually the ability of entrepreneurs and, according to some authors, the information factor includes and thereby emphasizes the role of information in the development of the economy. Our in our opinion, it is more correct to replace the opportunities of entrepreneurs with innovations or to connect both new factors with traditional factors. Current production by studying the factors, the analysis is carried out in depth and each factor is broken down. Earth or using natural factors as the basis of entrepreneurship is a

long-term competitive advantage are factors that do not provide advantages. In addition, many types of natural resources is non-renewable and may expire after some time. On the other hand, the innovative factor is practically inexhaustible and it creates innovations, them can be put into production; their expansion is long-term can provide competitiveness, because it is new, especially developed at the moment based on factors. In fact, such a point of view cannot be called "absolutely new". It was mentioned above a nalyzing the factors of production, "Sey" emphasizes the role of the entrepreneur, because he coordinates the following factors of production: land, capital and labor.

English scientist G. A. Hobson expressed this idea more vividly, creative abilities included in production factors. New products appear in the economic system the part where new markets will appear and new technologies will be introduced analyzed and called it "the field of progressive production". Now we innovate it we call economy. \

Of course, in the process of studying such a phenomenon as innovation, two scientists, namely N. Kondratiev and the names of J. A. Schumpeter from Austria should not be forgotten. It is Schumpeter himself. The first definition of the concept of innovation in the study of "Theory of Economic Development" gave. It is an existing development aimed at solving innovation commercial problems

interpreted as a scientific and organizational combination of output factors. Schumpeter directly noticed the source of development of economic systems in innovations. Because it is unique content innovation is a change that focuses on five typical changes, pointed out:

- 1. New technologies, new technological processes or new productionsupply markets;**
- 2. Introduction of products with new features;**
- 3. Use of new raw materials;**
- 4. Organization of production and material and technical support of production changes;**
- 5. Emergence of new markets.**

In addition, he uses the concept of innovation as a change explained that its purpose is to create new types of consumer goods, new production and introduction of vehicles in the form of new production organization and from them is to use. When describing innovation, Schumpeter always emphasized the role of the entrepreneur in this process has emphasized, because it is the

entrepreneur who is the driving force of new inventions is the implementer of the practice and the recipient of the benefit as a reward.

Not all inventions become innovations. Innovation is profitable and the market are inventions that satisfy the demand. In other words, done because of science an incremental idea is born, and the next step is to commercialize the idea, the invention turns into innovation, brings income. It says: if science is money. Innovation is the process of turning knowledge into money with added value is a transformative process.

Research methodology

In the article, the methods of scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction used. The data of this research is obtained from official sources and a well-known economist comparative analysis of scientists' theoretical views on the role of innovations in economic development, generalization of foreign experiences and in our country innovative based on the results obtained on the progress made learning entrepreneurship was achieved.

Analysis and results

If our country has developed countries with innovative processes. If we compare the situation, at present, the developed countries of the world have been for more than 15 years influenced by the innovative economy and the fifth technological cycle (long wave), is coming Only the countries that have access to the fifth wave, even what should they do after that?

First of all, they conduct scientific research in new high-tech areas will they reach these countries? Apparently, this is very problematic. However, this of these countries, especially in our country, created by other countries to the use of technologies and in the development of their economy use, as much as possible for foreign investments to enter the country Creating conditions is an obstacle to trying to overtake developed countries does not Vir some time ago this experience in Japan, South Korea and others implemented in countries. Indeed, provided by innovation opportunities and positive aspects of globalization, primarily South Korea, Southeast Asia such as Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore (often called "tigers") won by the states, as well as the Celtic "tiger" - in the field of innovation Ireland is one of the leaders. These countries are a paradigm for Uzbekistan can serve as, because our country is a small market, poor from its competitive unique unconventional resources with conventional resources it can develop successfully only if it chooses an innovative way using it can develop successfully only if it chooses an innovative path.

The competitiveness of the country is the competitiveness of individual enterprises develops based on Every enterprise has a competitive advantage uses his strategy to achieve. However, successful companies. The nature of evolution and development will be similar because companies innovate create competitive advantages based on In the enterprises of our country

The reason for the weakness of innovative processes is the influence of the following factors:

➤ low number of scientists working in industry, as well as in the labor force

low percentage of scientists and researchers;

➤ not to enter the field of high technology patenting;

➤ weak cooperation between the production sector and universities;

➤ relative failure to encourage innovation and entrepreneurship

operation of support mechanisms;

➤ complex procedures for starting a business; quality of technological education

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Also the concept of the so-called "European innovation paradox" from world experience it should be noted - on the one hand, gross investments in education and science when assessing its share in the domestic product, as well as most of the European Union percentage of people with higher education in the population of their countries, from the USA or Japan even better. Europe also surpasses them in terms of indicators of scientific potential (e.g. Nobel laureates, SCI publications, scientists with Ph.D number). Nevertheless, the productivity of the economy in the European Union is higher than that of the United States twice as low, its trade balance with the US is negative. From different parts of the world incoming students are trying to study in higher education institutions of the USA. Joint

States themselves are highly successful in using innovation, knowledge created not only in their own country, but also in the whole world commercialize.

To sum up, innovative entrepreneurship and It is modern, using foreign experience and introducing innovations into the production process. In enterprises, wages are 2-3 times higher than traditional enterprises, productivity is 2 doubled, especially the quality of life of workers compared to before and the fact that their well-being is ensured is positive of today's innovative economic reforms showing its sides.

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